

RESEARCH NOTE

NEW EVIDENCE OF ARTIFICIAL MOUNDS IN THE STILT VILLAGES OF BRAZIL, EASTERN AMAZON

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Figure 1. Map of distribution of Maranhão stilt villages and Lontra stilt village. Source: LARQ/UFMA.

ABSTRACT. Artificial mounds in pre-Columbian America provide evidence of stratified societies as chiefdoms and states. These structures served multiple purposes, including as burial grounds. For the first time, artificial mounds have been identified by the use of geotechnologies at the Lontra stilt villages in eastern Amazon, Brazil.

KEYWORDS. Pre-Columbian Mounds, Geotechnologies, Drones, Stilt Villages, Amazon.

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Figure 2. Artificial mounds 1 and 2 located on the bank of a paleochannel in the Lontra stilt village and test pit with pottery.

*Somewhere, something incredible
is waiting to be known.*
Carl Sagan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Stilt villages are a kind of unique archaeological site in Brazilian wetlands (Navarro 2018). The research team conducted fieldwork in November 2024, during the dry season, when lake levels decrease substantially. A systematic survey of the elevation of Lontra stilt villages was performed with reference to both present-day and historical sea levels (Figure 1).

1.1 Field RTK Data Acquisition and Drone

High-precision topographic data were acquired using Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) GNSS, which allows differential corrections in real time. The dual-frequency RTK GNSS system consisted of a rover (mobile unit) and a base (fixed unit). While the rover was deployed in the field, the base was positioned along the isoline marking the upper limit of the mangroves in the region. Considering that the tidal range may reach up to 8 m in the area (Tábua de Marés 2025), the topographic reference level was assumed to be approximately 4 m above mean tide. Corrections were received in real time via the NTRIP network, using local reference stations.

1.2 Field Season Planning

Prior to data acquisition, the current elevation of the mangrove closest to the Lontra archaeological site was

measured with RTK. Before topographic data collection, the following were defined: 1) coverage area and distribution of Ground Control Points (GCPs); 2) safe and representative locations for temporary base installation or NTRIP station access; and 3) time windows with stable weather conditions.

1.3 Data Collection

The rover measured the positions of GCPs distributed evenly across the study area. Each point was occupied for at least 10 minutes, allowing for signal convergence and fixed corrections. Data were collected with an expected horizontal and vertical accuracy of ± 2 to ± 5 cm and recorded in digital spreadsheet forms.

1.4 Drone

Drone surveys were conducted using a DJI Phantom 4 Advanced, equipped with a 20 MP RGB FC6310 camera with a mechanical shutter, capable of producing images with a resolution of up to 3 cm/pixel at 100 m altitude. Flights were autonomously programmed with the camera oriented at 90° , 80% frontal and lateral overlap, a flight altitude of 100 m, and a speed of approximately 30 km/h. Analyses were conducted in Global Mapper 22.1.2, using tools such as the Feature Information Tool and Search Vector Data to extract elevation and apparent reflectance in the RGB bands. Vertical accuracy of DTM elevation values (Z_{dif}) was evaluated as the difference between model-estimated values (Z_{DTM}) and measurements at GCPs (Z_{GCP}), according to equation 1 (Cohen *et al.* 2021):

$$Z_{\text{dif}} = Z_{\text{DTM}} - Z_{\text{DTM}} \quad (1)$$

1.5 Integration with SRTM Data and Orthomosaic Classification

Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) data, with a spatial resolution of 30 m, were integrated to provide a regional altimetric context.

2. RESULTS

During DTM generation for the Lontra stilt village, the team identified two archaeological mounds: Mound 1) an area of 527 m², elevation of 1.38 m, maximum diameter of 26.6 m, minimum diameter of 23.5 m, and a volume of 352 m³; Mound 2) an area of 740 m², elevation of 1 m, a maximum diameter of 35 m, a minor

diameter of 24 m, and a volume of 213 m³. A 30 cm-diameter test pit was excavated on Mound 1 using a hand auger to verify the presence of pottery (Figure 2).

3. CONCLUSION

Artificial mounds represent a form of long-lasting monumental architecture produced by various Amerindian societies and provide evidence of stratified social organization, such as chiefdoms and early states. The application of geotechnologies allowed, for the first time, the identification of two mounds containing archaeological material, such as pottery, at the Lontra stilt villages in eastern Amazon. Future archaeological excavations may clarify whether the structures were constructed as foundations for houses or served as burial sites.

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